

A matrix method based on the Fibonacci polynomials for solving fractional differential equations

S. Sabermahani*, Y. Ordokhani

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University,
Tehran, Iran

Abstract

This paper is concerned with deriving an operational matrix of fractional-order derivative of Fibonacci polynomials. As an application of this matrix, a spectral algorithm for solving some fractional-order initial value problems is exhibited and implemented. The properties of Fibonacci polynomials are presented. The operational matrix of derivative and product are given. This matrix is then utilized to reduce the solution of the fractional differential equations (FDEs) to a system of algebraic equations. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the technique.

Keywords: fractional differential equation, Fibonacci polynomial, operational matrix of fractional-order derivative.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2010): 34K28 , 34A08, 11B39.

1 Introduction

Ordinary differential equations involving fractional order derivatives are used to model a variety of systems, of which an important engineering application lies in viscoelastic damping [1]. The operational matrices of derivatives of various orthogonal polynomials are widely used for solving various kinds of differential equations. To be more precise, these operational matrices are used for solving both linear and nonlinear ordinary and fractional differential equations [2]. The Fibonacci polynomials and their related polynomials are of interest. In addition, the celebrated Fibonacci numbers and golden ratio appear in several applications in different fields of applied science [3].

Consider the following fractional differential equation:

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha y(x) + y^{(k)}(x) + y(x) = f(x) \\ y^{(r)}(0) = c_r, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $r = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1, k = 0, 1, \dots, m, m - 1 < \alpha \leq m$.

*Speaker(oral): s.saber@alzahra.ac.ir

2 Preliminaries and notation

2.1 properties of fractional calculus

In this study, the fractional derivative of $y(t)$ is understood in the Caputo sense [4]. The caputo derivative has the following property for $n - 1 < \alpha < n$

$$D^\alpha t^k = \begin{cases} \frac{k!}{\Gamma(k - \alpha + 1)} t^{k-\alpha}, & k \geq \alpha, \\ 0, & k < \alpha. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Some relevant properties of Fibonacci polynomials

The Fibonacci polynomials can be defined by many ways. For example, they can be generated with the aid of the recurrence relation

$$F_{n+2}(x) = xF_{n+1}(x) + F_n(x), \quad n \geq 0,$$

with the initial values $F_0(x) = 0$, $F_1(x) = 1$, and they also can be generated by the following form representation:

$$F_n(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor} \binom{n-j-1}{j} x^{n-2j-1} \quad (3)$$

Also, the following inversion formula to (3) in which the polynomials x_i is expressed in terms of the Fibonacci polynomials is of interest

$$x^m = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} (-1)^i \left[\binom{m}{i} - \binom{m}{i-1} \right] F_{m-2i+1}(x). \quad (4)$$

3 Operational matrix of derivative

Suppose that the equation (1) has a continuous function solution that can be expressed in the Fibonacci polynomials $y(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k F_k(x)$, and let $y_n(x)$ be an approximation to $y(x)$, that is

$$y(x) \simeq y_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k F_k(x) = A^T F(x), \quad A^T = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n+1}], \quad F(x) = [F_1(x), F_2(x), \dots, F_{n+1}(x)]^T.$$

3.0.1 Fibonacci operational matrix of derivative

The r -th order derivative of (1) can be written as [5]

$$y^{(r)}(x) = A^T D^r F(x), \quad D = [d_{ij}] = \begin{cases} i \cdot \sin\left(\frac{(j-i)\pi}{2}\right), & j > i \\ 0, & j \leq i, \end{cases} \quad r = 0, 1, \dots, n. \quad (5)$$

D is $n \times n$ operational matrix for the derivative.

3.1 Fibonacci operational matrix of fractional derivative

The caputo derivative of the vector F can be expressed by

$$D^\alpha F(x) = B^{(\alpha)} F(x) \quad (6)$$

where $B^{(\alpha)}$ is the $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ operational matrix of fractional derivative. In this section, we derive matrix $B^{(\alpha)}$. Using (2)-(4) for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$

$$D^\alpha F_{i+1}(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \binom{i-j}{j} D^\alpha x^{i-2j} = \begin{cases} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \binom{i-j}{j} \frac{\Gamma(i+1-2j)}{\Gamma(i+1-2j-\alpha)} x^{i-2j-\alpha}, & i-2j \geq \alpha, \\ 0, & i-2j < \alpha. \end{cases}$$

If $i-2j \geq \alpha$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D^\alpha F_{i+1}(x) &= x^{-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \binom{i-j}{j} \frac{\Gamma(i+1-2j)}{\Gamma(i+1-2j-\alpha)} x^{i-2j} = x^{-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \binom{i-j}{j} \frac{\Gamma(i+1-2j)}{\Gamma(i+1-2j-\alpha)} A_{ijk} F_{i-2j+1-2k} \\ &= x^{-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} B_{ijk} F_{i-2j+1-2k}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$A_{ijk} = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i-2j}{2} \rfloor} (-1)^k \left[\binom{i-2j}{k} - \binom{i-2j}{k-1} \right], \quad B_{ijk} = \binom{i-j}{j} \frac{\Gamma(i+1-2j)}{\Gamma(i+1-2j-\alpha)} A_{ijk}.$$

Therefore

$$D^\alpha F_{i+1}(x) = \begin{cases} x^{-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} B_{ijk} F_{i-2j+1-2k}, & i-2j \geq \alpha, \\ 0, & i-2j < \alpha. \end{cases}$$

where $D^\alpha F_{i+1}(x)$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$ is row's matrix $B^{(\alpha)}$.

4 Numerical method

In this section, we describe in detail how the operational matrix of fractional derivative of Fibonacci polynomials can be employed for solving fractional differential equations. Substituting approximation obtained into (1), we find that

$$\begin{cases} B^{(\alpha)} F(x) + A^T D^k F(x) + A^T F(x) = f(x), \\ A^T D^r F(0) = c_r, \quad r = 0, 1, \dots, m-1. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Now, (7) can be solved for the unknown a_i 's by using collocation with nodes $x_p = \frac{p}{n}$, $p = 1, \dots, n$.

5 Illustrative test problems

In this section we apply the method presented to solve the following test examples.

Example 5.1. Consider the following equation

$$\begin{cases} y''(x) + D^{\frac{3}{2}} y(x) + y(x) = 1 + x, \\ y(0) = 1, \\ y'(0) = 1. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

We applied the Fibonacci polynomial approach to solve (8) with $n=2$. In this case we have

$$F = [F_1(x), F_2(x), F_3(x)] = [1, x, x^2 + 1], \quad A = [a_1, a_2, a_3]$$

$$D^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^{(\frac{3}{2})} = x^{-\frac{3}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} & 0 & \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$A^T D^2 F + A^T B^{(\frac{3}{2})} F + A^T F = f(x),$$

$$y(0) = \sum_{k=1}^3 a_k F_k(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = \sum_{k=1}^3 a_k D F_k(0) = 1.$$

By using collocation method, we obtain a_i 's and we have $y(x) = x + 1$, which is the exact solution.

Example 5.2. Consider the composite fractional equation

$$D^\alpha y(x) = y(x) - x^2 - \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} x^{2-\alpha}, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (9)$$

with the initial condition $y(0)=0$. We applied the Fibonacci polynomial approach to solve (9) for different values of α . Using Section 4, we convert (9) to the system

$$A^T B^{(\alpha)} F + A^T F = -x^2 - \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} x^{2-\alpha}$$

If we set $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ and $n=2$, by collocation and using initial condition, we obtain $y(x) = x^2$ which is the exact solution.

Conclusion

The aim of present work is to develop an efficient and accurate method for solving fractional differential equations. The problem has been reduced to solving a system of algebraic equations. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the technique.

References

- [1] Bagley R.L. and Torvik P.J. (1983), Fractional calculus: a different approach to the analysis of viscoelastically damped structures, *AIAA J.* 21, 5 741–748.
- [2] Wang W. and Wang H. (2015), Some results on convolved (p, q)-Fibonacci polynomials, *Integr. Trans. Spec. Funct.* 26, 340–356.
- [3] Youssri Y.H. and Abd-Elhameed W.M. (2016), Spectral solutions for multi-term fractional initial value problems using a new Fibonacci operational matrix of fractional integration, *Progr. Fract. Differ. Appl.* 2, 2 141–151.
- [4] Keshavarz E., Ordokhani Y., and Razzaghi M. (2014), Bernoulli wavelet operational matrix of fractional order integration and its applications in solving the fractional order differential equations, *Appl. Math. Model.* 38 6038–6051.
- [5] Koc A.B., Cakmak M., and Kurnaz A. (2014), A matrix method based on the Fibonacci polynomials to the generalized pantograph equations with functional arguments, *Advances in Mathematical Physics*, 1687–9120.